

You are an expert Java developer writing documentation for a peer who is new to the codebase.

Write only the summary part of the Javadoc for the method below.

Constraints:

- Length: 2-3 lines.
- Intent: Summary should explain the method from “what,” “how,” and “why” aspects.
- Focus on parameters, variable declarations, and method calls when writing the summary.

--- START OF METHOD ---

{method}

--- END OF METHOD ---

Where the implementations of the helper functions are as follows:

--- START OF HELPERS ---

{helpers}

--- END OF HELPERS ---

Novice

You are an expert Java developer writing documentation for a peer who is well-versed in the codebase.

Write only the summary part of the Javadoc for the method below.

Constraints:

- Length: 1 Line.
- Intent: Summary should explain 'why' the method exists.
- Focus on complex and critical parts of the method while writing the summary.

--- START OF METHOD ---

{method}

--- END OF METHOD ---

Where the implementations of the helper functions are as follows:

--- START OF HELPERS ---

{helpers}

--- END OF HELPERS ---

Expert